

Comparison of the composition profiles of the low explosives in India from forensic exhibits and a brief discussion on preventive forensic techniques[†]

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Abstract : More than 1650 pre blast and post blast exhibits were analyzed using routine analytical procedures supplemented by advanced analytical techniques like Ion-Chromatography (IC) (mainly), Scanning Electron Microscope with Energy Dispersive X-ray Analyzer (SEM-EDXA), Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) (for a number of samples) for inorganic constituents and High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC), Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS), UV-Visible Spectrophotometer, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC/MS/MS) for organic constituents. Results of the investigations suggested that high explosives like nitroglycerine, di and tri nitrotoluene (DNT and TNT), tetryl, cyclonite (RDX), pentaerythritol tetranitrate (PETN) were rarely used except in mortars and detonators. Common easily available unrestricted chemicals like potassium nitrate/chlorate (KNO₃/KClO₃), arsenic sulphide (As₂S₃), sulphur, aluminium powder of different mesh size and sodium, calcium, magnesium, barium, strontium (Na⁺, Ca⁺, Mg⁺, Ba⁺, Sr⁺) nitrate with varying compositions along with splinters were used.

But there were perceptible changes in the modus operandi of the terrorists. There had been a spurt in the use of different types of ammonium nitrate (AN) based explosives like AN, AN+Al, ANFO (ammonium nitrate and fuel oil/diesel/kerosene), AN+wax, AN based gel/emulsion/slurry explosives with other ingredients. Urea nitrate was also obtained.

The article contains a brief description of works on AN+wax, AN based emulsion and uranium nitrate based explosives sent to CFSL and examined in the laboratory of CFSL.

Aspects relating to ascertain the trace of the origin of the explosives by determining the 'isotopic signature' of the elements (C, N, O, H) in the explosives and biomarker fingerprinting of the petroleum products in the explosives were discussed. Figures relating to the quantitative estimation of the compounds of the explosives and some experimental figures related to the validation of the experimental findings have been incorporated.

However, in view of increased terrorist activities and development of new arsenals, it is desirable to make on spot examination of explosive residues using high sensitive explosive detection system (EDS) and explosive trace detection (ETD) techniques.

Restriction and proper monitoring of the explosive materials and the desirability of undertaking counter terrorism or preventive forensic protocols to limit terrorist activities are needed.

Keywords : Ammonium nitrate, biomarkers, composition profile, emulsion/gel explosives, explosive detection system (EDS), explosive trace detection (ETD), ion-chromatography, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, SEM-EDXA, preventive forensics.

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

Highlights :

- Partial crime scenario and examination of explosives between 2006-2011.
- Paradigm shift from low explosives to ammonium nitrate and uranium nitrate based explosives.
- Absence of high explosives or peroxide based explosives.
- Use of isotopic signature and organic biomarkers for source determination.
- Emphasis on preventive forensic.

Introduction

Explosives are energetic materials which can burn at a high speed and the energies of chemical reactions can be harnessed both for useful and destructive purposes. The use of explosives for military and para military purposes in addition to their use for peaceful civil and commercial purposes like construction of roads, bridges, tunnels, mining, quarrying, seismic surveys etc. are well known. In fact, modern civilization owes much to the explosives.

Homemade explosives or IEDs (Improvised Explosive Devices) used by the terrorists were highly variable ranging from pyrotechnics to high explosives assembled with readily available unrestricted chemical constituents. Killing spree with automatic AK 47 rifles and other sophisticated weapons had also been observed in USA and other countries of Asia, Africa and Europe. But most of the destructive operations were made using Improvised Explosive Devices (IEDs) all over the world. Exhibits from other countries are always beyond reach and local exhibits available in India (a vast country with 125 crore population). However, indiscriminate use of IEDs by terrorists and other organized groups are the cause of alarm for human civilization. Widespread destructive activities like mass killing and demolition of religious places, historic architectural antiquities have been on the rise internationally and particularly in India, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Iraq, Palestine, Syria in Asia and Egypt, Nigeria and Tunisia in African countries and other neighbouring places involving vast population.

There had been a continuous flow of pre blast and mainly post blast explosive materials from the crater of explosion sites as forensic exhibits to Central Forensic

Science Laboratory (CFSL), Kolkata to ascertain the nature of explosives, their chemical compositions and ascertain the possible source or origin of the explosives.

Kuila *et al.*¹ reported the results of forensic analysis of about 1000 samples of explosives and post blast residues obtained during the period 1990-2000.

However, extremist activities were unabated particularly in middle and eastern region of India as evidenced from the receipt of more than 1650 forensic exhibits during the period 2005-2011 by CFSL, Kolkata for analysis and report.

In this work, an attempt had been made to

- (I) Classify the forensic exhibits in terms of inorganic, organic and mixed explosives and to ascertain the possible combinations of explosive ingredients used in pre blast and post blast cases following the standard protocols of forensic analysis using different analytical techniques.
- (II) Present a suitable compositional profile of improvised explosive based on studies reported here.
- (III) Ascertain the origin or places of compilation of explosives using isotopic signatures and biomarker fingerprinting, persons involved in these clandestine operations and the modus operandi of different terrorist groups or criminal outfits in different parts of the country.
- (IV) Suggest possible precautionary or monitoring measures to minimize explosive compilations and uses.

The results are reported in this article.

Materials and methods :

Chemicals :

Sodium hydroxide, hydrochloric acid and other inorganic chemicals were of A.R. grade of Merck. Ultrapure deionized water of resistivity 18.2 M Ω was used for preparing aqueous solutions. The samples were filtered using 0.45 micrometer Pal Gelman filter paper. NIST traceable multication and multianion reference standards were used for the preparation of standard solutions of ions for the calibration and estimation of ions using Ion-Chromatography.

Materials :

Materials were Improvised explosive devices (IEDs), unexploded (pre blast) explosives and mainly post blast explosive residues or debris sent to CFSL, Kolkata. Materials like jute strings (burnt or unburnt) with splinters like iron nails and balls, jalkathi, stones, glass pieces, small metallic containers of jarda (perfumed chewing materials containing tobacco), aluminium cans, intact or broken pieces of metallic pipes, iron particles, aluminium etc. collected from the different sites of explosions were isolated after physical examination before analysis of debris according to scheme given in flow Chart 1. The standard samples of high explosives were collected from High Energy Materials Research Laboratory, Pune (India).

Scheme for isolation of ingredients :

Isolation of ingredients of the explosives clearly indicated the presence of three distinct groups of explosives, e.g.

- (i) Water soluble explosives but insoluble in acetone or diethylether with solid ingredients.
- (ii) Partially water soluble and acetone/diethylether soluble, i.e. mixed explosives with solid ingredients.

- (iii) Insoluble in water but soluble in acetone/diethylether with solid ingredients.

Analysis of inorganic explosives

For the analysis of inorganic materials in the exhibits routine tests for metals and non-metals/ions extracted in water were performed using standard methods given in the literature¹⁻⁵.

The presence or absence of the elements or ions like sodium (Na^+), potassium (K^+), ammonium (NH_4^+), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), barium (Ba^{2+}), calcium (Ca^{2+}), aluminium (Al^{3+}), ferrous (Fe^{2+}), ferric (Fe^{3+}), manganese (Mn^{2+}), arsenic (As^{3+}), chloride (Cl^-), nitrite (NO_2^-), nitrate (NO_3^-), chlorate (ClO_3^-), perchlorate (ClO_4^-), sulphate (SO_4^{2-}), permanaganate (MnO_4^-), sulphide (S^{2-}), thiocyanate (CNS^-) and other ions in the extracted samples of explosive materials and post blast residues were established. However, every forensic investigation must be authenticated or validated by confirmatory experimental tests using sophisticated instruments. The instruments were formatted as per specification of the manufacturers of the instrument. NIST traceable standards were used for instrument calibration and estimation purposes.

Chart 1

Confirmatory tests for the presence of ions like K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} in the extracted exhibits and their quantitative estimations were made using ion chromatography (IC), a method recommended by FBI⁴. Calibration of the ion-chromatograph were made with the standard solutions of ions. However, SEM-EDXA and FTIR measurements were also used for confirmatory tests in few cases.

Analysis of organic explosives and fuels⁶⁻⁸

For the analysis of inorganic materials in the exhibits routine tests for metals and non-metals/ions extracted in water were performed using known methods given in the literature.

Preliminary identifications of the organic explosives usually in sub microgram range were based on color reaction extensively used in the field of explosive analysis. Many of the organic explosives formed charge transfer complexes with characteristic colour. 3,3-iminobis propylamine was used as charge transfer chromogenic agent in the TLC analysis of 2,4-nitroaromatic explosives and 5-nitromusks (not explosives but cosmetic products of wide use)⁹. However, nitromusks give purple color with alcoholic potassium hydroxide but no colored complex with 3,3-iminobis propylamine^{9,10}. Similarly, dinitro or trinitro benzenes give purple or purple red charge transfer complexes (initially named as Meisenheimer complex)¹¹ with 30% potassium hydroxide in ethanol or acetone solution. RDX, HMX give violet color with chromatropic acid and concentrated sulphuric acid.

In general, the explosives were subjected to TLC experiments and the spots were developed with suitable color reagents, e.g. 1% diphenylamine in concentrated sulphuric acid. Nitramines and nitrate esters producing deep blue color or spots were treated with potassium hydroxide solution followed by sulphanilic acid and 1-naphthylamine to give pink colored complexes. Confirmatory tests for identification were made using HPLC, HPTLC, GC-MS and LC/MS/MS (in few cases)¹²⁻¹⁶. However, spherical solid glass beads, paper balls, gum beads, guttapurcha beads, solid cardboards were not analyzed.

Instrumental analysis :

Systematic instrumental analysis of the exhibits was

done using instruments given in Table 1 following standard procedures and literature and also following the procedures suggested by the manufacturer of the instruments.

Results

It is impossible to give data with experimental details. Table 2 gives a comprehensive data of explosives comprising more than seventeen hundred exhibits and the classification (into group A-G) and number of exhibits in each group according to the presence of ingredients. Exhibits also contained detonators, hand grenades and mortars. Figs. 1 and 2 represented the typical ion-chromatograms for the cations and anions. SEM-EDXA curve of an experimental exhibit was shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 represented the size of aluminium in aluminium powder used in gel explosives using electron microscope. Representative Figs. (5a, 5b, 6 and 7) of HPLC, GC-MS, LC-MS-MS of different exhibits were shown. The year wise graphical representations of the number of exhibits of different classes were given in Figs. 8, 9a and 9b. Many of ammonium nitrate based explosives did not contain fuel oil, but the presence of wax in many such exhibits was confirmed using GC-MS and fluorescence measurements.

The mixed explosives were mainly NH_4NO_3 based gel or emulsion explosives containing MNT, DNT, TNT, stabilizers, low and high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons or wax as confirmed from TLC, HPLC, HPTLC, GC-MS studies though few exhibits contained TNT, tetryl and RDX.

Discussion :

The examination and analysis of the collected forensic exhibits are challenging as no evidence or prior information of these blasts is available. Sample collections from the debris (at the explosion sites) are difficult as many evidences and components of explosives were lost as a result of extensive disruption, damages of the locations of explosions due to fire caused by explosions and fire fighting operations like water flushing, use of foams etc. These might cause washing and dissolution of unburnt incendiary materials. Thus, only traces of residual components of incendiary materials with impurities were available for analysis.

Table 1

Sl. No.	Analytical method	Parameter	Analytes
1.	Chemical test (screening test)	(a) Spot tests for organic explosives in acetone extract (b) Spot tests for inorganic anions and cations	Common organic explosives viz. RDX, TNT, NG, PETN, Tetryl, HMX, DNT ^{3,8,12} Sodium, potassium, ammonium, calcium, strontium, magnesium, aluminium, arsenic, antimony, nitrate, nitrite, chlorate, chloride, sulphate, sulphite, thiosulphate, permanganate, perchlorate ^{1,2}
2.	IC	Metrosep A supp 3 column (for anion), cation 1-2 column (for cation) and Nucleosil 5SA column (for transition metal ions) 3 mM tartaric acid and 0.5 mM oxalic acid solution for cation 1-2 column with a flow rate of 1 ml/min, 1.7 mM sodium carbonate and 1.8 mM sodium bicarbonate buffer solution for Metrosep A supp 3 column with a flow rate of 1 ml/min and 3.5 mM oxalic acid and 2.5 mM ethylene diamine and 5% acetone (pH = 4.0) for Nucleosil 5SA column with a flow rate of 1 ml/min	Sodium, potassium, ammonium, calcium, strontium, magnesium, nitrate, nitrite, chlorate, chloride, sulphate ^{4-5,13}
3.	TLC/HPTLC	Mobile phase (Toluene : cyclohexane :: 7 : 3 or Benzene : acetone :: 99 : 1), stationary phase (silica gel 60F ₂₅₄ plate), visualization (diphenylamine in acetone)	Common organic explosives viz. RDX, TNT, NG, PETN, Tetryl, HMX, DNT
4.	HPLC	Mobile phase (Acetonitrile : water :: 7 : 3), column C18, PDA detector, flow rate 1 ml/min	Common organic explosives viz. RDX, TNT, NG, PETN, Tetryl, HMX, DNT
5.	GC-MS	EI ⁺ mode, source temperature 150 °C, energy 70 eV, mass range scanned 30–400 amu. Injector port temp. 180 °C, oven temp. 70 °C (1 min hold) to 280 °C (5 min hold) at 15 °C/min increment or 70 °C (1 min hold) to 280 °C (10 min hold) at 10 °C/min increment	Common organic explosives viz. RDX, TNT, NG, PETN, Tetryl, HMX, DNT, fuel oil, wax etc.
6.	FTIR	MCT detector working at 77 K. The scan range was 4000–700 cm ⁻¹ having a resolution of 4 cm ⁻¹	Unexploded pure explosives
7.	SEM-EDXA	Secondary electron mode (SE) with magnification 10000–20000, filament (tungstein or Lab ⁶)	Unexploded low explosives, pyrotechnic materials
8.	Spectrofluorimeter	Fluorescence measurements were made with Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer. The instrument was first standardized and calibrated with fluorescein	Fuel oil and wax of the gel explosives
9.	LC-MS-MS	LC-MS-MS measurements were made with 3200 QTRAP LC-MS-MS system of Applied Biosystem (MDS SCIX)	Post explosion residues of high explosives

Table 2. Constituents of exhibits and their number obtained during the year 2005-2009

Sl. No.	Type of explosives	No. of exhibits
(A) Chlorate based		
1.	Simple potassium (or sodium) chlorate (obtained as unexploded explosive substance)	101
2.	Potassium (or sodium) chlorate + arsenic sulphide and/or aluminium and/or sulphur and or charcoal (obtained as unexploded explosive substance mixtures)	91
3.	Potassium (or sodium) chlorate + arsenic sulphide and/or aluminium and/or sulphur and or charcoal + degraded or decomposed product of chlorate mixture such as K^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} etc. (obtained as post explosion residues)	94
4.	Only degraded product of chlorate mixture such as K^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} etc. (obtained as post explosion residues)	10
(B) Nitrate based		
1.	Potassium nitrate + arsenic sulphide and/or aluminium and/or sulphur and or charcoal (obtained as unexploded explosive substance mixtures)	144
2.	Potassium nitrate + degraded or decomposed product of nitrate mixture such as K^+ , NO_2^- , SO_4^{2-} etc. (obtained as post explosion residues)	146
3.	Only degraded product of nitrate mixture such as K^+ , NO_2^- , SO_4^{2-} etc. (obtained as post explosion residues)	126
(C) Chlorate + nitrate mixture		
1.	Potassium chlorate + potassium nitrate and sulphur and/or arsenic sulphide and/or aluminium and/or charcoal (obtained as unexploded explosive substance mixtures)	36
2.	Potassium chlorate + potassium nitrate and sulphur and/or arsenic sulphide and/or aluminium and or charcoal and/or their degraded or decomposed products such as K^+ , NO_2^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} etc. (obtained as post explosion residues)	97
(D) Ammonium nitrate based (slurry, gel and emulsion explosives) (water based or oil-in-water based)		
1.	(i) Ammonium nitrate + high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons (fuel oil) (ii) Ammonium nitrate + high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons (wax) (iii) Ammonium nitrate + high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons (fuel oil or wax) and aluminium	165
2.	Ammonium nitrate and aluminium	84
3.	(i) Ammonium nitrate + nitrate of other materials (such as magnesium, calcium, potassium, sodium etc.) (ii) Ammonium nitrate + nitrate of other materials (such as magnesium, calcium, potassium, sodium etc.) with aluminium (iii) Ammonium nitrate + nitrate of other materials (such as magnesium, calcium, potassium, sodium etc.) with high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons (iv) Ammonium nitrate + nitrate of other materials (such as magnesium, calcium, potassium, sodium etc.) with high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons and aluminium (v) Ammonium nitrate + nitrate of other materials (such as magnesium, calcium, potassium, sodium etc.) with high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons and aluminium and their degraded or decomposed products such as K^+ , NO_2^- , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} etc.	113
4.	(i) Ammonium nitrate + sensitizer (such as TNT, DNT, MNT, NG, PETN etc.) and high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons	56

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Table-2 (contd.)

(ii)	Ammonium nitrate + sensitizer (such as TNT, DNT, MNT, NG, PETN etc.) and aluminium	
(iii)	Ammonium nitrate + sensitizer (such as TNT, DNT, MNT, NG, PETN etc.) with high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons and aluminium	
(iv)	Ammonium nitrate + sensitizer (such as TNT, DNT, MNT, NG, PETN etc.) + nitrate of other materials (such as magnesium, calcium, potassium, sodium etc.) + natural gums (as gelling agent) + thickeners (fatty acid or their ester) + gum beads or rubber beads with high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons and aluminium	
(E) Urea nitrate		
1.	Urea nitrate	4
(F) Organic explosives		
1.	Secondary explosives such as Tetryl, TNT, RDX etc.	88
2.	Detonator (electrical) including aluminium and copper shell	256
	Detonator (non-electrical) including aluminium and copper shell paper detonator	81
(G) Ingredients of explosive mixtures seized		
1.	No explosive was obtained but the exhibits contained one of the ingredients of explosive mixtures such as sulphur, arsenic sulphide, aluminium, charcoal etc.	16

Fig. 1. Ion chromatogram for anion of a low explosive (mV vs time in min).

It is known that a mixture of oxidizer, fuels (used separately or present in the same molecule as in nitro explosives) and sensitizers in correct proportions make an explosive and explosive power is very much dependent on the strength of the oxidizer and burning power of

fuels. They are classified as low explosives and high explosives^{17,18} depending on the speed known as velocity of deflagration for low explosives like black powder, potassium chlorate, potassium permanganate and velocity of detonation for high explosives at which explosives

Fig. 2. Ion chromatogram for cation of a low explosive (mV vs time in min).

decomposed. Usually, explosives with velocity of detonation greater than 1000 m/s are known as high explosives (RDX, HMX, TNT, PETN, Tetryl etc.).

In earlier periods and till date, about 80% explosions all over the world including high profile explosions in India, Spain, England, USA, Indonesia, Bali, Australian embassy in Jakarta were based on easily available unrestricted inorganic chemicals like K/NaClO₃ (Chlorate powder with aluminium powder, sulphur etc.), K/NaNO₃, perchlorates, permanganates, chromates, peroxides, fuels like charcoal, magnesium, zinc, titanium, As₂S₃, other nitrates, boron, red phosphorous (to increase the heat of combustion). Kuila *et al.*¹ reported the results of forensic analysis of about 1000 samples of homemade or IED explosives and post blast residues obtained during the period 1990-2000. The trend is still unabated as evidenced from the analysis of about 1700 exhibits with chlorate based (296) and nitrate based (549) explosives with lesser variations in the present study. Permanganates, fuels like magnesium, zinc and organic fuels like starch were used rarely. Red phosphorous, antimony sulphide and sugar were not found in the explosives.

Importance and extensive uses of low cost unrestricted

inorganic chemicals in common homemade explosives (IEDs) had been described^{1,19}.

Dickinoski *et al.*⁴ emphasized the need of proper analysis of inorganic ions using sophisticated and accurate techniques like IC and CE (capillary electrophoresis) with modified light emitting diode to enable indirect photometric detection of elements. The importance of development of the advanced IC techniques and improvised columns for improved analytical results was stressed. However, the use of advanced instrumental methods like AAS, ICP-MS and SEM-EDXA were used for very small amount of inorganic ions in our laboratory.

Works of Kuila *et al.*¹, referred by Dickinoski *et al.*⁴ and the present investigations clearly indicated that military or commercial explosives like NC (nitrocellulose), NG (nitroglycerine), MNT, DNT (mono- and di-nitro toluene), TNT (trinitrotoluene), Tetryl (2,4,6-trinitro phenyl methyl nitramine), RDX (1,3,5-trinitrocyclohexamine), HMX (1,3,5,7-trimethylene trinitramine), PETN (pentaerythritol tetranitrate), SEMTEX and C4 (RDX/PETN with a plasticizer) had very restricted use by the terrorists or criminals.

However, ever since the devastating explosions caus-

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Fig. 3. Image and spectra of a lead sample obtained by SEM-EDX analyzing system.

ing heavy casualties in ships S. S. Grand Champs and S. S. High flyer loaded with fertilizer grade ammonium nitrate (AN) in the harbor of Texas city (April 1947) and S. S. Ocean Liberty in the Brest harbor (France, July 1947)¹⁶, low cost AN based formulations were extensively used as blasting agents thus phasing out dynamites (based on nitrocellulose and nitroglycerin explosives) for commercial and peaceful blasting purposes with better performance. This made perceptible changes in the modus operandi of the extremists abroad and in India (in the last decade). AN based explosives had been extensively used in Okla-

homa (USA), Northern Ireland, London, Manchester, Birmingham, Spain, Oslo (Norway)^{18,20} and in large parts of India like Delhi, Mumbai, Gujarat, Pune, West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Andhra Pradesh, Pakistan and Afghanistan and some other West Asian countries.

(a) **Ammonium nitrate based explosives**¹⁹⁻²² :

Extensive use of Ammonium Nitrate (AN) has been made all over the world in different forms.

- (i) AN as such or with Al as auxiliary fuel.

- (ii) ANFO (AN + usually with fuel oil No. 2, but other petroleum products are also used).
- (iii) Gel and emulsion explosives, the latter are much in use.

Prilled AN with 7–10% porosity to absorb 5–6% fuel oil for maximum explosive power and efficiency or less costly and less efficient fertilizer grade AN prills with 3% porosity to soak less fuel were much in use.

Fig. 4. Image of aluminium separated from a gel explosive obtained by electron microscope.

But, now a days, powdered AN and market available ordinary wax had been used extensively in eastern region of India and probably in remote areas like Gujarat, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Iraq, Syria and in other West Asian and African countries.

Prilled AN beads are separated by 'air gaps'; more energy is required for the shock waves to travel between the air gaps, i.e. energy booster is required for initiation of blasting. Wax can act as a better binder to eliminate air gaps than fuel oil for powdered AN. Infact, most of the explosives received by CFSL, Kolkata between 2005-2008, were AN + wax based explosives and not ANFO as reported previously.

The presence of wax was established from the following facts observed on reexamination of unexploded explosives and fire debris of the exhibits²¹.

- (i) Ethereal extracts of the exhibits on evaporation gave solid wax residues.
- (ii) Comparison of the TICs of the GC-MS profiles of the ethereal extracts of the unexploded bombs with those, i.e. of the ethereal solution of the normal wax confirmed the presence of wax as fuel in the fire debris of the explosives.
- (iii) Fuels present in the ethereal extracts showed blue fluorescence characteristics of wax. Fuel oils show no fluorescence.

However, the short comings due to air gaps (mentioned before) were obviated with improvised mixtures based on powdered AN mixtures in slurry/emulsion explosives usually thickened by guar gum or other gum with any cross linking agent or in gel explosives (containing any cross linking agent for polysaccharide thickener). Different proprietary commercial gel/emulsion explosives containing different compositions of AN (36–70%), NaNO_3 (10–15%), CaNO_3 etc. are known but not considered as the terrorists or other organized groups prefer locally made improvised emulsion explosives using ingredients locally available or procured locally where the transportation of ingredients and the disposal of IEDs are easy.

Gel or emulsion explosives examined in CFSL, Kolkata contained concentrated solutions of AN, K/NaNO_3 , $\text{Ca}^{2+}/\text{Mg}^{2+}$ and other nitrates (usually 50–55%), high boiling fractions of hydrocarbons (but not fuel oil) with a little petrolatum (mineral gelly) or gum acacia (not guargum) and a small amount of decanoic acids (like myristic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid or their esters having good emulsifying properties)¹⁹.

The explosive powers of the explosives were enhanced by sensitizers (mostly DNT but sensitizers like MNT, TNT, PETN or NG (rare) in very small amounts were also observed in some exhibits¹⁹. But no proprietary sensitizers were used. Slurry/emulsion and gel explosives were found to contain 7–9% finely powdered or paint grade Al to increase the explosive power of the explosives. The smaller the size of the Al powder, the greater is the detonation velocity. The sizes of the Al powder were in the

Figs. 5a and 5b. Chromatogram and spectra obtained by HPLC analysis of a cake explosive containing RDX.

range 200 nm to 800 nm (measured with the help of an inverted microscope of high resolution after passing the powdered suspension of Al in water through 0.22 μm membrane filter papers¹⁹. The sensitivity of explosives was enhanced by the presence of phenolic rubber like micro balloons and small glass balls with crushing strength. Other extraneous ingredients were not considered.

Ingredients of gel explosives can easily be transported for mixing or after mixing to the site of action and can be wrapped properly like proprietary explosives. In gel or emulsion explosives, water acts as a continuous medium. Ingredients come in close contact and increase the explosive power. Energy evolved is increased enormously with Al as auxiliary fuel. Military explosives like RDX, TNT,

Fig. 6. TIC of an ANFO sample-(relative abundance vs time in min).

Tetryl etc. were rarely used by the terrorists in India. Terrorists assembled IEDs from readily obtainable ammonium nitrate based explosives like ANFO, gel and particularly emulsion explosives¹⁸⁻²³ from readily available ingredients in general. The ingredients usually used were ammonium nitrate (AN), sodium/potassium/calcium/magnesium nitrates, fuels (kerosene, diesel, mainly ordinary wax relatively high boiling fractions of petroleum hydrocarbon), aluminium powder. Ordinary gums like gum acacia but not guar gum, solid gum beads, synthetic gum beads, rubber beads and surfactants etc. were also used^{21,22}. However, sugar, starch, micro balloons, glass or gas balloons or proprietary amines were not used.

The detonation power of explosives obviously depended on the charge (i.e. with a high packing density) and ingredients like aluminium, fuels, gum beads etc.

(b) Urea nitrate based explosives :

The recent trend showed the gradual use of urea nitrate (uronium nitrate) instead of AN due to ease of its preparation from readily available fertilizer urea. Urea is a fuel but urea nitrate is a powerful explosive (90% as powerful as TNT) with detonation velocity 11200–15400 ft/s depending upon charge size and confinement.

Urea nitrate was used in Peru by the Shining Path in car bombing and other terrorist attack in Palestine and in the bombing of the World Trade Centre (New York City, 1993). Recently use of urea nitrate based explosives (initiated by paper detonator) was also observed²⁴⁻²⁷. The highly acidic character of urea nitrate (not urea) causes color change of bromocresol blue from blue to yellow but the formation of yellow pigment due to reaction be-

tween *p*-dimethyl amino cinnamaldehyde or *p*-aminobenzaldehyde under neutral conditions is the confirmatory tests for uronium nitrate.

Attempts were made to distinguish urea and uronium nitrate from IR measurements which showed characteristic shifts in the peaks, formation of new absorption bands and disappearance of some of the peaks²⁸. The main changes should appear for C=O group due to formation of C-O⁺H. But, IR measurements could not be profitably utilized to examine the blast samples containing tracer of UO⁺H and urea. The presence of urea could be confirmed from GC-MS analysis whereas for urea nitrate or uranium nitrate only urea can be detected²⁸.

(c) IEDs consisting of organic explosives only :

Military explosives like RDX, TNT, Tetryl, PETN, NG etc. were rarely used but those were used in detonators, mortars etc. However, peroxide explosives like diacetone diperoxide (DADP), triacetone triperoxide (TATP) and hexamethylene triperoxide diamine (HMTD)^{17,18} were used in the attempted bombing in US Airline (December 2001) or in Casablanca, Morocco (July 2003) and in Israel by the Palestinians. Peroxide based explosives are of limited use all over the world as they are unstable, hazardous, and highly sensitive and prone to accidental initiation. No report for the use of peroxide based explosives had been made in India so far. The bar diagram and Table 1 also showed that in recent years most of the explosives used for massive destruction were ammonium nitrate based and urea nitrate explosives. Uses of these explosives are likely to be increased in future. A brief description of the composition of some of the explo-

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Fig. 7. TIC and m/z ratio of a RDX sample obtained by LC-MS-MS analysis.

Fig. 8. Pie diagram of no. of cases against year.

sives is given in Table 2 (categorized in different groups).

(d) Methods of ascertaining the origin of the explosives²⁹⁻³³ :

One of the main objectives of the forensic scientists is to trace the origin of explosives (the sources of explosive materials and fuels used or places of preparation of explosives and persons associated). Comparison of 'isotopic signatures' (isotopic ratio of C, N, H, O) of elements in the explosive materials can be utilized for the purpose.

Sharma and Lahiri³¹ determined the 'isotopic ratios' of C, N, H of different explosive residues from FTIR spectra of 77 K using MCT detector.

However, IR-MS (Isotopic Ratio-Mass Spectroscopy) is the specific instrument for the purpose. Reports of the use of Isotopic mass ratio in forensic analysis are :

- (i) Discrimination of ammonium nitrate sources³⁰.
- (ii) IR-MS preliminary study of TATP and PETN³².

Isotopic ratio analysis of the explosive urea nitrate and its precursors are known but without much success³³.

However, the presence of biomarkers^{21,34} in petroleum products like oils or wax and the determination of biomarkers in fuels of different origin had been found to be a good indicator of the origin of fuels or waxes in explosives or in arson cases. The aspect is yet to be explored properly.

Biomarkers or molecular fossils found in oils are diagenetic alteration products of their precursors (terpenoids, sterols, steroids etc.) in living organisms and they

are highly resistant to chemical, physical, thermal and biological degradations. Biomarkers in oil decipher informations regarding type and age of the source rock that generated the oil^{21,34-37}.

There are a large numbers of biomarkers in oils from different sources. Different biomarkers characterize the different sources (obtainable from petroleum research institutes).

Biomarker fingerprinting of fuels from different sources by GC-MS indicated the presence of different biomarkers. Amongst the large numbers of biomarkers, characteristic biomarkers were observed in arson cases of different region, e.g. Friedelane-3-one (to some extent squalene) (Delhi area), 14-B pregnane together with Hop-22 (29)-3-beta-ol (Southern West Bengal), Cadalene (North Bengal and North-East region). Similarly, a definite biomarker 28-Nor-17beta(H)-hopane (C₂₉H₅₀) was observed in wax of exploded bombs examined and in market available wax in the Midnapore and Jharkhand areas (terrorist infested regions).

However, the aspect has not been properly considered and needs careful investigations. It is desirable to prepare a comprehensive data base of distinct biomarkers in petroleum products of different origin and also isotopic ratios of C, N, H, O of compounds of different origin to have a positive say regarding the sources and persons associated in the preparation of explosives.

Before concluding the paper, it is desirable to mention that challenges from organized criminal and extremist groups have been gaining momentum with simultaneous developments in the preparation of explosive arsenals (IEDs) for nefarious purposes. It is desirable to locate explosives before they are operative.

Counter terrorism measures³⁸⁻⁴³ :

It is desirable to have on site examination of the explosive and residues from the fire debris. Trace explosive vapors and explosives should be examined by non destructive analysis using portable instruments like NIR (near infrared spectra), IMS (Ion mobility spectrometer), and fluorescence kits. It may be necessary to eject involatile solid into atmosphere by a laser ablation device and detect trace explosive vapors.

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9a

Fig. 9(a). Graphical presentation of no. of cases and nature of exhibits against year.

9b

Fig. 9(b). Bar diagram of no. of cases and nature of exhibits against year.

But under ordinary conditions, emphasis should be given to explore the use of field operative portable IC, CE, NIR

and IMS for rapid on spot analysis of forensic exhibits. However, confirmatory test should always be done using

IC, SEM-EDXA, ICP-MS for inorganic explosive constituents and GC, GC-MS, LC-MS, optical spectroscopy like FTIR and Raman spectroscopy for organic explosives in forensic laboratory.

Raman spectroscopy and its portable unit is a valuable tool for non-invasive forensic investigations of chemical and biological hazardous materials and can be used for pre blast and post blast improvised explosive devices.

Human scent specific canine teams can be utilized to locate and identify individuals having contact with improvised explosive device (IED) components and/product delivery vehicles. Pre blast and post blast explosives may be located with suspected individuals.

It is difficult to have culprits with or without explosives in police custody for punishment by the judiciary.

According to Saferstein⁴⁴, crime laboratories run on physical evidences collected from the crime scene. In a court of law, it is required to provide proof in a criminal case that is "beyond a reasonable doubt" or in civil matter "the preponderance of evidence" supports the conclusion⁴⁵. In recent years, forensic examination schemes or protocols are dictated not only on technical considerations but also the recognition that procedures must meet the requirements of the legal systems.

The forensic problems are complex and there is no single answer. The techniques to be used must all be acceptable to the scientific community and the main errors associated with particular methods must be understood and eliminated if possible. It has been accepted that a single analysis is insufficient to make an identification but the number required depends on how mutually exclusive the techniques are⁴⁶.

Conclusions

Analysis of post blast residues and explosive materials suggests that even now the majority of homemade IED explosions were due to chlorate and nitrate based low explosive mixtures with As_2S_3 , S, Al etc. In recent years, there has been an increase in the use of ammonium nitrate based explosives particularly emulsion explosives and urea nitrate based explosives with high destruction capabilities.

The materials were unrestricted and easily procurable compounds which did not come under the explosive substance act 1908 of India. However, inorganic materials mixed with organic materials were also observed, but use of high explosives like TNT, PETN, NG, RDX, Tetryl etc. was rare. Some precautionary suggestions are :

- (I) The sale of $KClO_3$, KNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and As_2S_3 should be restricted and monitored.
- (II) Analysis of inorganic explosives should be carried out with IC with better column, SEM-EDXA and CE modified with light emitting diode (not used by us) preferably with portable NIR instrument with adequate software.
- (III) Examination of explosive residue should preferably be carried out on spot with portable IC, NIR (near infrared spectroscopy, portable Raman spectroscopy and other instruments).
- (IV) Better explosive detection systems (EDS) and explosive trace detection (ETD) should be used as counter terrorism measurements. NIR and IMS (ion mobility spectroscopy) are capable of determining traces of explosives in the vapour state and involatile solid may be ejected into atmosphere by laser ablation device.
- (V) Emphasis should be given for the identification of source materials using isotopic mass ratio of the elements in the explosives and identification of biomarkers in the fuels.
- (VI) Environmental contaminants should be carefully monitored.

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